

HOW TO BE CREATIVE

**Can we develop musical creativity in education
and self-teaching?**

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Jazz Piano, MA

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A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'B. Thiébault', written in a cursive style.

Abstract

Benjamin Thiébault

HOW TO BE CREATIVE

Can we develop musical creativity in education and self-teaching?

Research lecture and symposium

This research is a survey of creativity and a proposal of the techniques that can be used for this purpose.

Abstract: “There is a large preconception from which people say that the creative act is spontaneous, that people should be either gifted or not. Considering the fact that everything can be practiced, and everybody is unique, how can we learn to develop our particularities within a specific context? How can one approach the desire to have an idea and turn the act of being creative into a routine? There is no method on how to have an idea. Such a method does not exist because the problem is not to get to know how to have an idea, or what can we do to have an idea because we cannot act directly on having ideas. Good ideas emerge on their own, not when we force them to happen. What we need to do is to work on the process which lies underneath, the engine that triggers the productive activity which is going to generate an idea. We need to make sure that when this idea arrives, we know how to catch it and how to develop it. We need to be able to recognize it as being a good idea, something which pleases us and that we want to experiment with. By approaching the phenomenon of creativity in a scientific way, by understanding the neuro-mechanics and the psychological principles through which we become creative, and by learning how we can train our mind, I will try to discover what we can do to enhance creativity as a biological fact. Then, by looking through the history of jazz and by identifying some of the main innovators, both traditional and contemporary, I will try to understand what is at the heart of the creative act and define its relationship to music and art through the concepts of improvisation and composition. Finally, by studying several systems of education which put their focus on creativity, I will try to highlight what we can take from them, in order to propose some recommendations to apply to our practice, teaching and institutionalized environment.”

Facilities needed for symposium: beamer, grand piano, sound system

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Introduction

What is creativity? How can we implement it in our practice routine? How can we learn and teach jazz music or music to be interpreted and improvised within today's institutionalized environment?

As a jazz student, I would first think that in order to become an accomplished musician, I need to learn the language of the music that I want to play. I need to master the technique of the instrument that I chose, to learn about music theory and to have some knowledge of what I am doing. I need to be aware of the rules which surround a moment of music, to know how to evolve within this specific environment and to have the freedom to choose what I want to express according to the framework that I am dealing with. How can I be ready - when the moment comes - to play, to compose, or to improvise? Is the material, and the tools that I have gathered beforehand sufficient enough for my musical soul to emerge? How can I be prepared to play something new in relation with a certain field of expertise to transform the past into the present?

In his "*Les cahiers de la créativité*", French researcher Guy Aznar wrote that the buzzword 'creativity' has emerged quite recently from an American psychologist named J. P. Guilford. When Guilford observed that what he considers as a form of intelligence was barely studied in the US at that time, he was convinced that creativity could be developed through education, and consequently, that it should be studied more.¹ Today, the global concept of 'creativity' has become a large part of our everyday life. Does this necessarily mean that we are more creative today than we used to be in the past? In fact, by approaching the idea of 'being creative', of doing something new and original by aiming directly for its result, by seeking 'creativity' as a single concept, we might be looking at the problem in the wrong way. Why do we need to be creative? For people like entrepreneurs, scientists and researchers, educators, artists and musicians, it has become a need to be creative. In the context of a fast-changing society, we need to learn how to adapt quickly to a new situation. We do not need to learn the techniques that have led us to a certain type of activity which our technologies are meant to gradually replace. The permanent competition which characterizes our society forces us to look for what is unique about each of us in order to mark ourselves out. More importantly, the only thing that we can work on doing better than the machines that we created and for what they cannot replace us is the act of being creative.

In his 1987 lecture "What Is the Creative Act", philosopher Gilles Deleuze made the following observations: first, having an idea is a "rare event", it does not happen that often; this means that if we are playing music for instance, and we are interpreting a melody, improvising a solo or accompanying a soloist, we shall not seek for the most brilliant idea to grab at every little second. We better prepare the field for it to spark. Secondly, Deleuze stated that having an idea is not something that happens "in general". It is dedicated to a certain domain, by someone who is himself doomed to that domain. Thus, an idea is a "potential that is already engaged in one or the other mode of expression, and according to the technique that we know and the knowledge that we have."² We can only be creative in a domain of expertise that we gained through time by studying, practicing and experiencing. In music and jazz, we need to

¹ Guy Aznar, *Les cahiers de la créativité*, France : Créa Université, 2014, p. 32

² Gilles Deleuze, *Qu'est-ce que l'acte de création*, Paris : La Femis, 1987, 47 min.

learn what has been here before, and integrate it at a level which is sufficient enough for building our own way of doing it. Finally, “creativity comes from a need.”³ If we relate this last idea to what we have introduced in the paragraph just before, here lies a paradox. What do we mean by ‘creativity’ in our time? Because we do not need to be creative today in a reaction to our former needs, modern creativity does not come *from* a ‘need’ – more, it is actually *the* ‘need’. We need to be creative today to invent what has to come as a logical step, the result of our prior necessity which is now fulfilled.

In his 1970 book “Poetics of Music in the Form of Six Lessons”, composer Igor Stravinsky explains what he considers as being creativity and freedom in music: “My freedom will be so much the greater and more meaningful the more narrowly I limit my field of action and the more I surround myself with obstacles.”⁴ To be creative, we do not only need to have a field of action to evolve in; we also need to restrict ourselves. Because we need vocabulary, and we always want to know more, and we sometimes think that the more material we have, the more we can use. (This is true, yet if I want to create something which makes sense, to improvise a good solo or to write music which sounds convincing, using an overabundance of ideas that I don’t know how to deal with, and putting them all together hoping that it will work does not mean that I am going to create something interesting). In that sense, the consideration of what defines greatness by emphasizing quantity over quality can be a mistake. The more musical material we gather, the greater the danger that this material overlaps and constricts our own creative impulse, preventing us from developing simpler ideas in a more deliberate way. Relatively to the jazz music practice, if I want to know how to play inside the chord changes of a song, I would need to learn the scales, chord substitutions, arpeggios, and every little possibility linked to the song that I am dealing with, in order to have ingredients that I can use during my solo. However, since this exploration is infinite and there are billions of possibilities from where I can start developing my solo, the goal should not be able to do everything, or to simply know all those possibilities - which is even worst -, rather than truly understand, explore and entirely integrate just a few of them. In that way, our goal should be to master the material that we use in a way that aim not only on the result motivated by a mean of perfection, but on an opened door. How about when it comes to composition? Let’s say that I want to write music. I probably need to learn what is consistent of a musical composition, to look at the process which is followed by the composers that I like, and to come up with something. This means that in both situations, I will have to emulate one of the great masters, let’s say to ‘copy’ one of my favorite players or composers so I can have a model to follow. Although having heroes and truly integrating their approach is important, it can also be dangerous to stay there for too long in finding your own identity. Therefore, we must keep an eye on ourselves and maintain our critical thinking, so that, rather than running forever after the greatness of the people we admire (and becoming a pale imitation in the process), we can develop our personality and find our own identity.

There is a large preconception that the creative act is spontaneous, that people should be either gifted or not. Considering the fact that everything can be practiced, and everybody is unique, how can we learn to develop our particularities within a specific context? How can one approach the desire to have an idea and turn

³ Gilles Deleuze, *Qu’est-ce que l’acte de création*, Paris : La Femis, 1987, 47 min.

⁴ Igor Stravinsky, *The Poetics of Music in the Form of Six Lessons*, New York, 1947, p. 160

the act of being creative into a routine? There is no method on how to have an idea. Such a method does not exist because the problem is not to get to know how to have an idea, or what can we do to have an idea because we cannot act directly on having ideas. Good ideas emerge on their own, not when we force them to happen. What we need to do is to work on the process which lies underneath, the engine that triggers the productive activity which is going to generate an idea. We need to make sure that when this idea arrives, we know how to catch it and how to develop it. We need to be able to recognize it as being a good idea, something which pleases us and that we want to experiment with. By approaching the phenomenon of creativity in a scientific way, by understanding the neuro-mechanics and the psychological principles by which we get to be creative, and by learning how we can work on our mind, I will try to discover what we can do to enhance creativity as a biological fact. Then, by looking through the history of jazz and by identifying some of the main innovators, both traditional and contemporary, I will try to understand what is at the heart of the creative act and define its relationship to music and art through concepts of improvisation and composition. Finally, by studying several systems of education which put their focus on creativity, I will try to highlight what we can take from them, in order to propose some recommendations to apply to our practice, teaching and institutionalized environment.

I. How Our Brain Works

1) The Neuroscience of Creativity

It is now scientifically proven: music is one of the activities which involve the most parts of our brain, from our memory to our imagination, body coordination, auditory and emotions. We often say that in the human brain, the left part (which is predominant) is dedicated to the rational thinking, whereas the right part is connected to our intuition. Realistically, it appears that in the process of creativity, both parts of our brain activity are involved.

What is at the heart of creativity? According to neuroscientist Beau Lotto, creativity thrives on what the brain fears most. Because “our brain has been made to ensure our survival, every behavior that we do, we do to reduce uncertainty. If we want to get to see differently, we need to understand the principles by how we see in the first place.”⁵ It is therefore necessary to understand what has been created before us, and to possess the specific craftsmanship that leads to a concrete result in order to secure our certainty of what is surrounding us. A study led in 2007 by psychologist Mihály Csíkszentmihályi, among others, shows evidence that inside the brain exists a set of frontal and temporal association areas which are specifically involved in the free creation of musical structures during improvisation. By asking eleven concert pianists to perform according to three conditions: improvise (on which the pianist improvised on the basis of a visually displayed melody), reproduce (the pianist had to reproduce his previous improvisation from memory) and improvise freely (the pianist was instructed not to memorize his performance), the psychologists discovered that the

⁵ Beau Lotto, *Creativity Thrives on What the Brain Fears Most*, New York: Big Think, 2017, 7 min.

process of creativity involves different parts of our brain at the same time, depending on which specific sort of thinking we use in order to create.⁶

What researcher Guy Aznar has defined relying on cognitive science is that in order to conceive something new, two kinds of thought processes are involved. First, the rational thinking which consists of putting things one after the other, to progress step by step by following a logical method and to generate solutions within a series of causalities. This way of thinking is omnipresent in science; it was constructed and developed by iconic philosophers such as Aristotle or René Descartes who have both heavily influenced Western society. By defining a system of thinking based on a methodic approach, Descartes prepared the ground for the great practical and atheist vision of the world that we have today, detached from the religious appreciation of reality, thus laying the foundation of our modern society. A variation of rational thinking is what we call associative thinking or lateral thinking. A powerful source of creativity, it consists of making analogies through the use of imagination, metaphors and images, to create ties between things that seem apart from each other but which possess similarities, and to connect them. It distinguishes itself from regular rational thinking by laying a foundation for a large number of possible solutions to a problem instead of converging towards a single answer. The second kind of logic that we have is creative thinking itself, which obeys the rules of hazard, intuition, unexpectedness, subjectivity and emotions.⁷

The research “Cortical Regions Involved in the Generation of Musical Structures during Improvisation in Pianists” makes an interesting distinction between an improvisation which would arise from a pre-existent material, encouraging variations, interpretations and the use of memory, over an absolutely free creation without any restriction. This distinction is to be related to the one we made between our two kinds of thought processes and the relationship to jazz music. In the first case (improvisation based on a visually displayed melody and memorization), different researchers have previously discovered an activation of the cortical association areas - more particularly, the right prefrontal cortex - in complex, verbal tasks which involve divergent thinking. In the case of a total improvisation, researchers have shown a number of cortical regions involved in free selection (such as willed action) with an emphasis on the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) which regulates attention, working memory and monitoring. The research based on piano improvisations suggests that in the free creation of musical structures, the DLPFC interacts with the dorsal premotor cortex (a part of the primary motor cortex) and the pre-supplementary motor area (pre-SMA). However, another study, “Stimulation of the Primary Motor Cortex (PMC) Enhances Creativity and Technical Fluency of Piano Improvisations” led in 2017 on eight proficient jazz pianists (4 females and 4 males, 6 right-handed, 1 left-handed and 1 mix-handed), states that this part of our brain (the PMC) is actually involved in the consolidation and acquisition of new motor skills, while also playing a role in mediating between creativity and technical fluency in the context of an improvised jazz performance.⁸ Thus, our capacity of inventing new musical objects always results from

⁶ Sara L. Bengtsson, Mihály Csíkszentmihályi, and Fredrik Ullén, *Cortical Regions Involved in the Generation of Musical Structures During Improvisation in Pianists*, Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience, 2007, p. 14

⁷ Guy Aznar, *Les cahiers de la créativité*, France : Créa Université, 2014, p. 32

⁸ Aydin Anic, William Forde Thompson, Kirk N. Olsen, *Stimulation of the Primary Motor Cortex Enhances Creativity and Technical Fluency of Piano Improvisations*, London:

the meeting of our two ways of thinking: the rational and associative, and the creative. We must let the unconscious part of our brain make the decisions and embrace the feeling of insecurity that it provides. We shall make the connection between those two logics easier and find a way to practice going back and forth from one to the other, in order to develop creativity. This feeling of 'letting go' should only happen after a long and continuous process of gaining expertise. We must master technique and knowledge through a long-time practice to create an environment which allows our intuitive and emotional state to release. Guy Aznar call this moment of stability the 'blue zone'. It is when imagination makes a compromise with reality that the human brain creates.

Figure 4. Brain regions active in the Improve–Reproduce contrast. Activity maps of brain regions with significantly increased BOLD contrast signal are shown for the right dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC; slice $y = 39$), the left superior temporal gyrus (STG; slice $x = -60$), and the bilateral dorsal premotor cortices (PMD; slices $y = 6$ and $z = 45$). The color scale shows t values. R and L denote the left and right sides, respectively. The histograms show mean percent signal change in BOLD signal for each condition in peak voxels of the active regions, with the Rest condition as zero. Error bars show standard error of the mean (SEM). Names of conditions are abbreviated as follows: B = Rest (baseline); I = Improve; R = Reproduce; F = and FreeImp.

Figure 5. The pre-SMA and improvisation complexity. In the pre-SMA, a positive relation was found between brain activity in the Improve–Reproduce contrast, and the degree of complexity of the improvisations, operationalized as the LED between improvisation and template. Adjusted fMRI data from the peak voxel of the cluster (the red cross in the activity map; $x, y, z = 12, 15, 54$) are plotted against mean improvisation complexity for each participant in the graph. Each dot in the plot represents an individual participant.

Source : Sara L. Bengtsson, Mihály Csíkszentmihályi, and Fredrik Ullén, *Cortical Regions Involved in the Generation of Musical Structures During Improvisation in Pianists*, Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience, 2007, p. 14

According to doctor Alice Flaherty cited in “Creativity and Innovation” by Christine Charyton, “creative drive will increase with moderate degrees of temporal lobe dysfunction in combination with increasing dopaminergic tone”. Even in neurosciences, a scientist must have “a vivid intuitive imagination for new ideas not generated by deduction but by artistically creative imagination” (Max Planck).⁹ When neuroscientist Beau Lotto stipulates that “the reality that we perceive is related to the context that we evolve in, the decisions that we make are linked to our reflexes grounded in our history” he considers that the way we see reality is already modified by our perception. Perception is the key to making our ideas work within the frame of reality, so to be able to work on our perception is one way to stimulate new thinking. “There is actually nothing creative in a creative act. It only looks creative from the outside, whereas from the inside, it is just about making a logical step to the most likely possible option, based on a certain search space, which is based on our assumptions. To challenge our creativity, we need to question our assumptions.” Because our assumptions never completely reflect the reality, the only way we can make something new is to challenge those assumptions. Our brain “cannot do big jumps: if you want to go to the next room, you have to walk” because “we cannot stop having biases.”¹⁰ Working on our creativity, or practicing creativity is the act of making biases which push us to be innovative.

Source : Christine Charyton, *Creativity and Innovation Among Science and Art: A Discussion of the Two Cultures*, United States: Springer London, 2015, p. 239

⁹ Christine Charyton, *Creativity and Innovation Among Science and Art: A Discussion of the Two Cultures*, United States: Springer London, 2015, p. 239

¹⁰ Beau Lotto, *Creativity Thrives on What the Brain Fears Most*, New York: Big Think, 2017, 7 min.

How do we apply this to music? What do we need to do to be creative within the process of improvisation? We need to create a space of uncertainty without trying to control where we go next, because “anything interesting begins with doubt.”¹¹ In order to do something concrete with it, we need to practice being in the feeling that it provides, whereas this feeling is fear or joy, and to try not to be surrounded by it. We shall find a way to be comfortable in this uncomfortable situation, to be trustful when we are uncertain. To provoke a zone of disorder and to be able to feel a balance inside it.

2) The Psychological Factor

Psychologists have been defining creativity in several different ways for the past twenty years, and amongst these is a theory made by cognitive psychologist Robert Sternberg. He stipulates that there are two central characteristics in a creative behavior: one, “creative acts are novel and original”, and two, “they constitute valuable contributions to the field”.¹² What defends Mihály Csíkszentmihályi on his 2008 TED talk on flow and happiness is that “we as artists embody the fact that it is worth spending our lives doing something for which many of us won’t expect either fame or fortune, and still find pleasure and lasting satisfaction.” For Csíkszentmihályi, “when we begin to create a new, alternative reality, we step in a state of ecstasy.” We get into a zone where we lose our consciousness. We lose our sense of time. We feel like above our own body. We forget ourselves and start doing things for their own sake. We get to a state of extreme focus and we know naturally what needs to be done, as we become serene against difficulties. This phenomenon of being in a zone of extreme focus and happiness is what Csíkszentmihályi describes ‘the flow’. To experiment with it, “we need to be trained. We can start by beginning to change something in a way that it is now better than it was before. We need to find a balance between the skills that we have in what we like to do and the challenges that we are dealing with in a certain situation. We need to make these challenges one small step higher than our average level. Thus, we encounter a constant and intrinsic motivation, as we start to roll in a circle of automatic and positive generation.”¹³

American jazz pianist Kenny Werner has written a book entitled “Effortless Mastery” in which he provides thoughts and exercises on what he calls the ‘act of surrender’ that leads to embracing freedom. Firstly, we shall work on our thoughts, in order for them not to obstruct the flow of the music. “Why Do We Play?” he asks. He argues that we should try to remember the first time we ever touched an instrument and felt good about it. Similarly, he believes the reason why sometimes people quit is that “just as abused children become abusive parents, music teachers force-feed dry information from generation to generation. The dryness of music in school causes young people to tune out”. Caring too much, forgetting the initial purpose of us playing is a natural consequence of playing for many years, in contexts where you feel like

¹¹ Beau Lotto, *Creativity Thrives on What the Brain Fears Most*, New York: Big Think, 2017, 7 min.

¹² Robert Sternberg, *Handbook of Creativity*, New York: Cambridge University Press, 1999, p. 490

¹³ Mihály Csíkszentmihályi, *Flow, the secret to happiness*, United States: TED Talk, 2008, 18:50 min.

being judged and criticized. If you don't play the right notes, or what the jury expects from you, you might fear not to succeed. As Kenny Werner says, "your whole system freezes" in such contexts, whereas when you are with friends that you trust, or people who really like you, you don't care much about proving anything, more than just pleasing you and those people who are listening to you. As soon as we try to control the result of what we play, every single note becomes a possible mistake. We get tensed, stressed, and we lose our focus which should rather be committed to what we are playing, to the process that we like and made us become a musician. We lose our ability to create something beautiful that is us, or to share music conveyed by the vector which we become. "Being able to speak in complete sentences is not an art, but a technical skill."¹⁴ It doesn't make you a poet. However, there is a long-standing controversy about this extemporal question. "Some people are afraid to learn too much for fear of losing their soul." Avoiding extreme self-criticism, being curious, feeling and not expecting, and loving everything you play is essential to Kenny Werner in the process of learning improvisation.

The Flow. After Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, *The Flow* (1990), p. 74

¹⁴ Kenny Werner, *Effortless Mastery*, United States: Jamey Aebersold, 1996, p. 194

How can we manage to play an improvised form of music deeply rooted in history while developing our personality? Music sounds good when the people that play it feel good. From the abovementioned research, we can see that creativity is often directly linked to our emotions, which is why we should be constantly listening to our deep inner voice when we play. Creativity is the ability to conceive something which is new, but it doesn't mean that something is required to be new in order to be creative. We can only create something which is linked to us if we know what we want and who we are while being related to a certain context. Researcher Sue Langley has led a study on the impact of emotions on creativity, based on the generalized hypothesis that "positive moods lead to higher creative output than negative". As correct as being positive helps in dealing with everyday life, and that creativity is a positive process giving fulfilment and enjoyment, she came to the conclusion that "creativity calls on persistence and solving skills, not positivity."¹⁵ As psychologist Mark Davis discovered through the study of the relationship between mood and creativity, while positive mood enhances creativity during the initial phase of gathering information, the 'good mood' doesn't improve problem-solving which involves judgments that won't necessarily feel good: critique, pressure, dealing with uncertainty, challenge, engagement, persistence, independence and experimentation.¹⁶ In a 2012 study led by computational scientist Anna Jordanous and language expert Bill Keller, 14 components have been identified in the creative process, three of them being stated as critical in music improvisation. One, the social interaction and communication on which they consider "promoting work to others in a persuasive and positive manner, sharing mutual influence and feedback, and collaboration"; two, the domain competence which is related to "domain-specific intelligence, knowledge, talent, skills, experience and expertise"; three, the intention and emotional involvement which is

¹⁵ Sue Langley, *The impact of emotions on creativity*, Australia: Langley Group, 2013 research report, p. 18

¹⁶ Mark A. Davis, *Understanding the relationship between mood and creativity: A meta-analysis*, United States: Department of Management, University of North Texas, 2008

“personal and emotional investment, immersion, self-expression and involvement in the creative process.”¹⁷ Therefore, this research conveys the idea that mood management is the key in the process of creativity, not happiness or purposefully-generated-stress. Intense emotional pressure, whether being good or bad, can cause distortion in our capacities of attention, decision making and creative thinking.

Source: Anna Jordanous, Bill Keller, *Modelling Creativity: Identifying Key Components through a Corpus-Based Approach*, United Kingdom: University of Kent, University of Sussex, 2016, p. 27

But what about the altered-state of mind that we know from legendary artists such as Vincent van Gogh or Antonin Artaud in the process of creativity? Whether it is engendered by an overwhelming emotion, drug-consumption or mental illness, an altered-state of mind is one psychological example of the creative spirit, which has been discussed in psychiatry through the works of Sigmund Freud and Carl Jung. In Jung’s “Psychology and Literature”, the artist is seen both as “a human being with a personal life and an impersonal creative process.” Then, the artistic creator is not only a distinctive person, but also embodies an impersonal force. “Since the artist’s work responds to the needs of his society, it has implications greater than those involving his own personal fate.”¹⁸ That is why a great work of art is always related to something moral, or intellectual, or anything else which is anchored in the contemporary times of the creator. It lies within something which is universal, and which can survive through time.

¹⁷ Anna Jordanous, Bill Keller, *Modelling Creativity: Identifying Key Components through a Corpus-Based Approach*, United Kingdom: University of Kent, University of Sussex, 2016, p. 27

¹⁸ Carl Gustav Jung, *Psychology and Literature*, Berkeley: University of California Press, 1985, p. 217-232

3) How to Educate the Mind?

We can divide our brain waves in 4 categories: first, the Beta Wave. It's the cycle of complete awakening (14 to 21 cycles per second). We are in full alert, conscious, and our brain is hyper-active. As soon as we close our eyes we get comfortable, our brain waves slow down and get to a cycle which is defined as the Alpha (7 to 14 cycles). Both hemispheres of our brain work more together and stabilize, thus reducing the predominance of the left part of our brain. If we slow down our cerebral activity a little more and reach the level of 4 to 7 cycles per second, we qualify that zone as Theta. This level of consciousness is associated to the light phase of sleep. Finally, below 4 cycles per second, we reach the state of unconsciousness, or deep sleep phase.¹⁹ What about the second phase which is associated to the Alpha Waves? The particularity of this state of mind is that, because our mind is relaxed, and both hemispheres are equally stimulated, we shall focus better, have a better capacity of memorizing things, have a better control on our stress or emotional states, and to be more creative. This phase called Alpha is what we try to reach by the use of hypnosis. Another method to reach a controlled and stabilized state of mind is through meditation, which we can find in different non-western cultures and practices such as Buddhism, Hinduism or Japanese Zen. It consists of an activity of observation, analysis and concentration, the aim of which is to awaken a very subtle level of consciousness and to use it to intuitively discover the reality around us. For instance, the end result of Mahayana Buddhist practice is to reach the 'Enlightenment': to feel love and compassion for all beings.²⁰

How can we apply these techniques to musical creativity? In fact, 'being in the zone' as described before is a form of meditation. By focusing on one sole thing, be it the great feeling of rhythm, a motif, or a player from the band - anything that we feel connected with or that we want to connect with - and by developing the ramifications that come out of it, we get into a state of mind which enhances focus, joy and pleasure. That is why an improvisation, or an interpretation or the act of generating ideas in composing music is so enjoyable. It puts us into a state of dedication which leads us to being creative.

II. Being a Jazz Musician

1) Some Historical Facts

What is Art? Where does it come from? How can we define it?

Creative art periods always merge themselves in a specific context. If we look through our recent history, the explosion of ideas within the romantic era is one example, whereas the great diversity and development that followed birth of jazz is one other. It is grounded in history and environment within a certain context, and there are reasons that generate the will to be creative. But today the need lies in creativity itself, because we don't need it anymore. How can we recreate the need of being

¹⁹ Aparnathi Rajendra & Vyas Ved, Dwivedi, *The study About Brain Wave Extreme Low frequency and Works*, India: CU Shah University, 2014, p. 15

²⁰ Kathleen McDonald, *How to Meditate*, United States: Wisdom Publications, 1984, p. 269

creative? Wide access to information through the internet, no gigs out there, considerations of jazz as a superior music... is there a need when there is no audience, when this form of popular music merged into conservatism, and people don't expect anything new from it? We rely on the fact that because we know how to play that difficult type of music, we can stay grouped and isolated, and it doesn't matter that much if people will not understand why what we are doing is hip. Because we didn't grow up in this environment during which jazz music was created, we miss the urge which defines jazz music and artistic creation. We're not playing on the same ring. How can we make this a statement for our case, today's 21st century, in an institutionalized environment?²¹

Philosophers in the likes of Friedrich Nietzsche and Albert Camus have contributed in looking to the artistic process which we can relate to jazz music history. Nietzsche has conceptualized a philosophy of aesthetics which consists of making a distinction between two forms of art, stating that the entire development of the artistic act is linked to the duality between them. The first one that he calls the Apollonian (in reference to Greek mythology and God Apollo, King of Art, Beauty and Music), and the second one he calls Dionysian (from Dionysus, figure of Excess and Madness). Through the coupling of both of those opposed divinities by means of a fusion between the rigorous and logical understanding and the intuitive aspect of artistic expression, the knowledge of art that we have in the ancient world has resulted in the tragic creative act.²² From Camus' writings, we may retain the idea by which the act of rebellion of a man in reaction to his lack of existence is a creative act. "If the rebel must refuse both the fury of the void and the consent to the whole, the artist must escape all at once from the formal frenzy and the totalitarian aesthetic of reality. [...] But that the creative act itself is necessary does not involve that it is possible. A creative period in art is defined by the order of a style applied to the disorder of a time."²³

How did jazz musicians and composers revolutionize music so that it got actually incorporated in the elitist academy of expertise? The reason it got so popular might be because it was new, and most of the jazz musicians wouldn't think of jazz music as a style, or an aesthetic. They thought of a spirit. In my opinion, the reason why jazz music is a creative form of art is because of: the merge of different influences that lead to create a new sound; the improvisational aspect which obeys to certain rules, put in a certain musical context of form, pulsation and harmonic changes; the ability to break those rules to create tension; the urge of playing what has to be played at the moment we play; the challenging aspect which is linked to its history; the necessity of having a personal voice; the ability to take one idea, and to bring it to its end using development; the social interaction; the feeling it provides. For all those reasons, I consider as a necessity to find some recommendations about having a creative practice routine which generates ideas and bring the player to a true and enjoyable state of improvisation.

²¹ Eitan Y. Wilf, *School for Cool*, London: The University of Chicago Press, 2014, p. 268

²² Friedrich Nietzsche, *Die Geburt der Tragödie aus dem Geiste der Musik*, Germany, 1872, p. 143

²³ Albert Camus, *L'Homme Révolté*, France : Gallimard, 1951, p. 384

2) Jazz Institutions Today

In his 2014 book entitled *School for Cool*, Eitan Y. Wilf describes how the academy of jazz education comes with a paradox. It is a complex challenge, reflective of a key problem in the cultural code of Western tradition, and the rationalization of creative practice. According to him, this paradox lies in the contradiction between the necessity that we can only transmit experience through 'story-telling', while with the advent of modernity, story-telling has been gradually replaced with information, "knowledge that is decontextualized from the life-world of those who consume it". He states that "in the past, novice jazz musicians would learn their craft by playing with seasoned musicians who had experiential knowledge of the music and its history. People who understood jazz tunes not only in terms of abstract melodies and chord changes, but also as musical entities embedded in specific histories that they have lived." The author comes with this first conclusion: the opposition between creative agency and institutionalized rationality is the product of modernity, which he describes as the increased rationalization associated with the Enlightenment in the 18th century and the expansion of ideals from creative agency associated with Romanticism in the 19th century. The first assumes a view of modernity as a technique, whereas the second understands human creativity as emotions being sources of action. "Jazz was born on the streets, yet it's at the academy where jazz is now flourishing that we shall embrace this contradiction between the institution and the act of creativity."²⁴

How to deal with the fact that great jazz masters have mostly disappeared and those who have been directly in touch with them are very few? How can they pass through what they have learned to keep the craftsmanship alive? The reason schools were created were both because of the demand for knowledge and understanding (how could it be that jazz as the popular music of its time was excluded from school's curricula?) and to create a new market.

Some institutions are more interested in trying to catch the sound of the old masters rather than competing at being creative (which was the original purpose), whereas in others, the opposite is the case. I believe we need both, because we cannot create otherwise. How to make a link? The inheritance of print pedagogy in the context of academic jazz education relative to western classical music training (described as 'charismatic authority' by sociologist Max Weber, according to Eitan Y. Wilf) is one explanation of this paradox. Students are not taught valuable knowledge in appropriate ways. Learning from the jazz masters is what we often miss in jazz education, because there are very few of those people who can teach today. In that sense, the 'charismatic authority' of classical music training which comes from print pedagogy could be seen as one that we as jazz musicians can get from iconic records. I believe it is important that we keep learning by ear and immerse ourselves in deep listening more than using print pedagogy - even if we should still know how to read - because that's the only way we can learn how to speak the language, and to gain insights into the act of improvising music. We can only improvise and create things that are real, original, personal, valuable and unique by hearing them in our head and knowing how to fit them in the context of reality.

Was Miles Davis a creative person? How can we take from him in order to be creative ourselves? What other examples of creators do we have in the jazz field? As

²⁴ Eitan Y. Wilf, *School for Cool*, London: The University of Chicago Press, 2014, p. 268

Miles Davis describes to Quincy Troupe in his Autobiography, the greatest feeling he ever had in his life was when he first heard Dizzy Gillespie and Charlie Parker play together. “The whole band would just like have an orgasm every time Diz or Bird played.” The first time he got to share the stage with them, he had trouble reading the music he had in front of him - because he was listening to what everybody else was playing. “I have come close to matching the feeling of that night in 1944 in music, when I first heard Diz and Bird, but I’ve never quite got there. I’ve gotten close, but not all the way there. I’m always looking for it, listening and feeling it, though, trying to always feel it in and through the music I play every day.”²⁵ In relation to the result of something creative “which only looks creative from the outside”²⁶, Miles Davis said that as complex as people try to make his music out to be, he likes it simple; that’s the way he hears it even if it’s complex for them. Learning from the Jazz Master who he is, we should bear in mind that trying, or attempting to make something cool, to sound like something or someone, to go somewhere special and to be original is not a pathway towards creativity. We shall explore and experiment without thinking too much. Like Herbie Hancock said about the times when he was playing with Miles Davis, you have to be yourself, and turn the music, the mistake, whatever you’re doing, to be music. In my opinion, the reason why Miles Davis was great is because he would never master in advance what he was doing. He was always on the edge of something new, non-academic, which would have been barely done before, nor studied, nor theorized. He would discover what he was doing *as he was doing it*, not *before* even trying. He would just have the courage to systematically challenge himself and the musicians who played with him, to never play what he has played before, or what he knows how to do already; to always experiment, be in the present, fuel his power of inspiration from these extremely strong ideas he had in mind and from those emotions he would get by connecting several different things together, before being guided by what he was hearing. As he described in his biography, one way of understanding such a mentality is to consider that he was constantly chasing this great feeling he once had by listening with extreme satisfaction to the music of Charlie Parker and Dizzy Gillespie.

3) A Few Individuals

In the documentary “The Universal Mind of Bill Evans”, the iconic pianist talks about his vision of the creative process. “Jazz is not so much a style than a process of making music.”²⁷ According to him, the biggest difference between a jazz improvisation and a musical composition is that in the first situation, music of a certain duration is written within that same duration, whereas in the second situation, a composer takes a much longer amount of time to write music compared to the final result. “Jazz is a process of making one minute’s music in one minute’s time, whereas when you compose, you can make one minute’s music and take three months.” Moreover, here lies the interesting particularity brought back by jazz musicians that could be used within an institutionalized environment. In order to start a process of creative playing, we first need to deal with something very simple, and to go step by step. As soon as

²⁵ Miles Davis with Quincy Troupe, dir., *The Autobiography*, New York: Simon & Schuster, 1989, p. 400

²⁶ Beau Lotto, *Creativity Thrives on What the Brain Fears Most*, New York: Big Think, 2017, 7 min.

²⁷ Louis Carvell, *The Universal Mind of Bill Evans*, United States: Rhapsody Films, 1966, 45 min.

we overlay, we do something approximate. We better do something which is real and satisfactory. Being creative is not about playing numerous, complex and sophisticated music. This looks more like an imitation of something which is creative, rather than a real creation. A creation “only looks creative from the outside” (as said by Beau Lotto). From the inside, it is a picture of honesty which starts with developing one single idea in a really dedicated and meaningful way. “Jazz in a way has resurrected that process [of improvisation and spontaneity, or spontaneous creativity]”²⁸ which was lost before in the Western tradition of classical music, started there originally but went far into making a separation between the composer and the interpreter, mostly for the reason that the art of composing grew big and took over improvisation, and that we could only eternalize great pieces of music that were spontaneous by writing them on paper. One last anecdote about how to be creative comes from the moment when Bill showed his brother Harry an example of how to play the changes in a certain context, and Harry revealing that many years later he would systematically play the same progression on this song every time. From that statement, we should realize that because we have everything easily accessible within a few clicks, we tend not to push Sisyphus' rock up the mountain ourselves.²⁹ The mystery which surrounds the magic of music tends to be lost. If we want to continue to be conjurers, we must force ourselves to let the secrets be revealed by advice and personal quest instead of simply giving one the answer. We must avoid using a short-term satisfaction that is not rewarding or constructive in the long term, but which will only last as it is, for a moment.

In the documentary “The Art of Improvisation”, Keith Jarrett discusses his relationship to music. He argues that “the more experience a person has the more simplicity is profound”. According to him, “timing is the complex part of simplicity”.³⁰ Music is moving through time. If we don't take that into consideration, we lose the aspect of spontaneity. We can only be anchored in the present moment in order to make something valuable. In the documentary “Language of The Unknown”, Wayne Shorter expresses that “to find the potential of anything, all those musicians have to be courageous and humble enough to not want to flaunt their musical credentials”. He says that “it's going to take as much courage from the audience to see the unexpected as we are thinking we are finding the way to use potential.” He argues that humility is the key to not overplay, and fearlessness the ability to welcome the unknown. “What we call a mistake is a start.”³¹

What Duke Ellington said is “I am not playing jazz. I am trying to play the natural feelings of a people.”³² For him, “popular music of the day is the reflector of the nation's feelings.” It is because jazz is anchored in a particular sociological context (such as racial segregation, poverty and lack of recognition) that it has resurrected what lies inside living music. Therefore, what we need to do to play creative music is not to belong to the past but to the present. Each time has its own considerations, and art is

²⁸ Louis Carvell, *The Universal Mind of Bill Evans*, United States: Rhapsody Films, 1966, 45 min.

²⁹ Albert Camus, *Le Mythe de Sisyphe*, France : Folio Essais, 1942, p. 187

³⁰ Michael Dibb, *Keith Jarrett: The Art of Improvisation*, United Kingdom: EuroArts, 2005, 84 min.

³¹ Guido Lukoschek, *The Language of the Unknown*, Germany: Avindependents, 2013, 56 min.

³² *The Duke Ellington Reader*, ed. Mark Tucker, New York: Oxford University Press, 1993, p.45

one of the best ways to express it. In a system invented by Ornette Coleman called 'Harmolodics', every single voice in an ensemble is equal. Sound is the fundamental principle of music, and there are no preferences put on any instrument. Inspired by the human rights in society and classified in the domain of free jazz, the aim is to focus on the emotion and the human connection as a source of creation³³ (for which we can refer back to Camus). The idea is to establish a state of collective improvisation, by freeing the players from any tonal center, to create the sensation of unison.

4) Artistic and Musical Renewal

Jazz music is strongly related to the recording era. During this era, people like Charles Mingus would learn how to play this music by playing along with the radio. It represented a market that has now almost disappeared and forced musicians to get to a result in a limited amount of time when entering the studio. In a way, creativity today is deeply linked to the numeric revolution.³⁴ But most of the time in art, the motivation comes from the envy of being a creator, to conceive and to give birth to something. It can sometimes speak for a cause or for a person. In music, inspiration comes from anything that is generating an emotion. It sometimes comes from the act of achieving a state of satisfaction, or perhaps prayer.

As described by guitarist Ben Monder in an interview given to writer Radhika Philip, "people wind up writing these books full of harmonic patterns and everybody out there is trying to have the greatest patterns to play out over certain chords, whatever". He continues with "it all gets very heady and intellectual. Whatever you figure out from all these books, I don't know, there really isn't too much emphasis on just having one not mean as much".³⁵ Musicians like John Coltrane and Ambrose Akinmusire seem to have wondered about finding their own voice, to dedicating themselves to something which is bigger than them. In that way, they give themselves to what has to happen when they play. Both are known to be extreme practitioners. They constantly try to tend to a supreme state of artistic expression, by infinitely trying to achieve a perfect mastery of their craft, knowing that they would never attain it because it's endless. They lead the boat through the ocean, but let the deeper currents guide them to where they are supposed to go next, in a moment of absolute openness. Shuffling things which are extremely diverse, or redefining techniques on their own instrument are part of a process used by artists like American pianist Craig Taborn or French guitarist Marc Ducret. In an interview for a keyboard magazine in March 2014, pianist Aaron Parks described what he defines as making living music. He breaks it down via an analogy to the human body: melody equals voice, rhythm equals body and heartbeat, and harmony equals mind. "The times that I enjoy making music the most are when all three are active and working together".

³³ Stephen Rush, *Free jazz, harmolodics and Ornette Coleman*, New York: Routledge, 2017, p. 302

³⁴ Matthew Homer, *Beyond the Studio: The Impact of Home Recording Technologies on Music Creation and Consumption*, United Kingdom: Nebula, 2009, p. 15

³⁵ Radhika Philip, *Being Here: Conversations on creating music*, United States: Unknown, 2013, p. 461

1. Before You Listen, Listen

When musicians speak of listening, it's usually *music* they're taking about. But what about the sounds and silences that exist *before* a note is even played? When I sit at the piano, I'll often first take some time to attune myself to the environment that I'm in. I notice the sounds that are usually ignored: air conditioning, birds, traffic, electronic hums, and more. This kind of aural meditation helps prepare me to be fully present and receptive to whatever happens next, whether it's listening to and interacting with other musicians, or going deeply into the interior in a solo piano context. Try it sometime and see how it feels for you. For further thoughts about listening in the more typical sense of the word, I highly recommend Ran Blake's book *Primacy of the Ear*.

2. Activate the Voice

First of all, *sing*. It doesn't matter whether you think you have a good voice. One of the best ways I've found to foster natural lyricism in improvisation is to play through the chord changes of a

tune, trading phrases between my voice and my right hand. At first it may feel like each has its own rather distinct identity, but eventually they'll start to influence one another and merge. Also, practice singing the melodies to songs in your repertoire and notice how you phrase things. It's remarkable how much about pianistic melodic interpretation you can learn from your own emotional intuition.

3. Activate the Body

My piano teacher, Sophia Rosoff, is one the greatest teachers of music I've ever encountered, and she has shown me many useful techniques to help connect to the body and bring the rhythm to life. Here's one. Take a piece of music you're working on and isolate what the left hand and right hand are doing. Then tap out the rhythm of the left hand part with both feet together, while simultaneously tapping out the right hand part with both hands. Play the piece again. Usually it feels different immediately—less like you're trying to force the rhythm to happen, and more like joining a dance that's already underway.

4. Activate the Mind

The mind is most often running the show, and doesn't need nearly as much encouragement. There are a few things, however, that I've found to be helpful in engaging the mind usefully. My favorite, by far, is transposing. Learning a tune in multiple keys makes you experience the harmonic movements as something more than just "chord changes." It becomes less about knowing which notes are "allowed" in one chord or another, and more about understanding the shifting colors of the song and the relational aspects of harmony. You can also make up little games for yourself to find your way out of mechanical habits while improvising. For example, take a solo using intervals of minor/major seconds and minor/major sixths only. And try to make it sound like music, not math.

5. Surrender

All of the things described above can be thought of as ways of preparing yourself for making music. Once everything is activated, just *let go*. It's a paradoxical thing. Let go of thoughts about whether what you're playing is "old" or "new," "good" or "bad," "derivative" or "original." Just be present to what the music is, what it needs, and where it wants to go. It has a voice, body, and mind of its own.

Individuals such as pianist Vijay Iyer, saxophonist Steve Lehman or flute player Magic Malik seem to be like researchers, in a pursuit of finding new material to try out. Pianist Ethan Iverson writes a blog where he puts everything he collects. By developing and bringing new ideas to use within an academic frame, they embody a very personal approach which provides a great example of searching for new material to be creative. Simultaneously, collectives such as M-Base (led by saxophonist Steve Coleman) and John Zorn's numerous bands are constantly seeking for new ways to stimulate musical creativity within a group of people. Being able to find those kind of settings is great for any jazz student who wishes to develop themselves through collaboration.

III. Creativity in Education

1) How to Stimulate Creativity

The way we learn our craft and get constant and easy access to wide information on the internet is amazing, but it can be dangerous, too. Speaker Ed Rex has shared his thoughts on questioning if computers can be creative. According to him, computers will be creative one day, but two major factors remain: firstly, "art is about more than the work itself". If the machine can do the work to replace the human, the work itself provided and the personality emerging from someone going deeply into the creative process cannot be replaced by the machines; secondly, "people will always be creative". Just because I'm not the best composer doesn't mean I stop caring about creating music. I will keep playing music because I love it.³⁶

We have great examples of how to stimulate creativity by looking at companies and entrepreneurs. When people want to work in a group in order to find solutions and solve a problem, and start with putting all their ideas together, we call it 'brainstorming'. The theorization of this technique which consists of gathering ideas comes from an American advertiser, Alex Osborn. The good aspect of it comes from the fact that in a situation where a lot of different people are involved, the idea of breaking the rise of one single ego is encouraged. It is, therefore, a true form of interaction that we can also find in some aspects of jazz music. Researcher Guy Aznar opposes this methodology with another way of creating ideas, which is known as 'synectics' and was popularized by psychologist William Gordon. In this methodology, the phases leading to finding a solution through different psychological states are known as analogies. The direct analogy, which consists on confronting facts, information or different disciplines; the personal analogy, the symbolic analogy and the fantastic analogy.³⁷ By then, the user of this technique should find new ways to create detours in their perspectives.

In his system called the "Six Thinking Hats", scientist Edward de Bono describes how to overcome a lack of ideas. He offers the idea that through dividing our thoughts in 6 categories towards one single problem, we can classify them and deal with one thing at a time. The White Hat corresponds to the 'information' because of its neutrality. The Red Hat is linked to feeling and emotion. The Yellow Hat is positivity. The Black Hat is associated to caution. The Green Hat is the alternative and the Blue Hat, the

³⁶ Ed Rex, *Can computers be creative?*, London: TEDx Talks, 2016, 14 min.

³⁷ Guy Aznar, *Les cahiers de la créativité*, France : Créa Université, 2014

coordination.³⁸ Therefore, solving a problem within a group consists of attributing one single and extremely clear role to each individual, while allowing each to create analogies. There are many more systems that have been invented to stimulate creativity in the business world. All of them possess some tricks that are worth taking the time to study, as they are proven to be extremely productive, although they don't fit with an artistic consideration of the creative act.

2) The Existing Systems

British educator Ken Robinson has done huge amounts of work in the field of creativity in education. He separates his research work in three categories, from the belief that we live in times of revolution and that we need to think differently about ourselves and our organizations. He is a strong believer in innovation for a better emphasis on people's creative powers. His belief comes from the observation that one consideration that we have is to build a system of education that takes into account the economy of our century, preparing people for the labor market, and to reform our system which has been designed for a different age (the industrial revolution). This former system put a lot of people full of potential on the side due to the pyramidal aspect of access to knowledge.³⁹

Italy's first woman physician, Maria Montessori, developed a scientific approach to facilitate early learning. Dedicated to children's education, the method consists of preparing an environment which allows the child to select one activity over many others, all of them being attractive. She emphasizes that the hand is the chief teacher of a child. In order to learn, there must be concentration, and one way to catch a child's attention is to make them use their hands.⁴⁰ We can relate this technique to another one made by Austrian philosopher Rudolf Steiner called the 'pedagogy of imagination'.

Medical doctor and psychiatrist Donald Winnicott has also emerged as a theorist in education which focuses on early learning. He believes in what he calls the self and the holding, both related to the relationship between a child and his mother. He would also make a distinction between creativity and the artistic creation. Finally, he distinguishes several kinds of impulse of creativity, including destruction.⁴¹ To live with a feeling of creativity, we shall have the feeling of being alive and ourselves. He doesn't see anything exceptional in an artist besides his talent for his craft, and he believes that this is only one way to express the creative potential which we have inside us. In that way, artistic and musical creation can reversely be an inspiration for individuals who suffer from a need of self-purpose and for our society. If we want artistic creation to develop wider, we need to educate the people for them to be capable of receiving what we have to offer.

³⁸ Edward de Bono, *Six chapeaux pour penser*, France : Interéditions, 1987, p. 207

³⁹ Ken Robinson, *Changing education paradigms*, United Kingdom: RSA Animate, 2010, 12 min.

⁴⁰ Maria Montessori, *The Montessori Method*, United States: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, Inc., 2004, p. 306

⁴¹ Donald W. Winnicott, *Home is Where We Start From: Essays by a Psychoanalyst*, New York: W. W. Norton Company, 1986, p. 288

3) Personal Recommendations

What can we take from science, psychology and philosophy for a better musical practice which enhances creativity? How can we learn from the Masters in our relationship to jazz? How can we translate the models of education that we studied into teaching music?

We need to evolve in an inspiring environment. To create, we need to restrict our freedom, and to surround ourselves with obstacles. To make the bound between the formal and the marginal; between order and disorder. To feel good about our surroundings. To focus on one thing at a time, and not to be distracted. To be caring, willful and to find interest in what we do. To be challenged, to step aside from our comfort zone and face with fear. To break our routine and to embrace the unknown. To lead ourselves to excitement, urge and self-esteem. To experience with feelings and emotions, and to transcend them. It is the act of shifting our mind from our implemented habits, ways of perception and education, automatisms and built-in assumptions that can lead us to see things differently.

We should bear this in mind in our relationship to music. We should make whatever we play meaningful, and leave ourselves open for our personal, intuitive and loving imagination. Practice how to stay in a zone of uncertainty, to walk in the dark and to play inside it. By constantly be looking for inspiration within all of the steps we need to go through in the process of learning how to play, and by linking the things that we care about to different identities, we can start to be innovative.

Conclusion

- Creativity is a form of logic which can be improved.
- Creativity is a human characteristic that technologies cannot replace.
- It is the ability of making connections between two things that are far apart from each other, to think in a multi-directional way and to make associations.
- It comes from the ability to let things be ruled by our emotions.
- The brain mechanics which result from a creative act show scientific examples of how in a particular context our creativity sparks.
- Art is the expression of a general wonder by a specific individual.
- We do art and music because we want to conceive something that makes us feel great and/or peaceful with our entity.
- In music, going somewhere which sounds good, feels good or at least different, and detaching itself from the zone we are evolving in creates tension.
- There is a concrete way of practicing how to deal with jazz music for playing with depth and build a unique and personal sound.
- We can work on our mind through techniques such as meditation.
- Creativity can be taught and stimulated within education.

It would be interesting to approach several jazz students to consider what they like the most in their practice routine, and to ask them to question themselves on what can they say about the things that lead them to be inspired and creative; to know what

they have been taught, told or exposed to in their early musical education that brought them to the willing of playing music, what is the root of their desire of creating music, and to make them remember the very first experience that triggered their choice of being a musician. Finally, using the information that is gathered in this research, one could find interest in creating a method for practicing creatively, rather than the concept of creativity itself.

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